

HOSPITAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract—Hospital Management System is a web-based application developed to simplify and automate the daily operations of a hospital. In many small and medium hospitals, patient records, doctor details, and medicine information are often managed manually, which leads to data loss, errors, and difficulty in maintaining records. The proposed system aims to provide a digital solution for managing hospital activities in an efficient and secure manner.

The main objective of this project is to design and implement a centralized system that can handle different modules such as Admin, Patient, Doctor, and Pharmacist. The system allows the administrator to manage users, doctors to view patient details, patients to access their information, and pharmacists to manage medicines and prescriptions. By using this system, the overall workflow of the hospital becomes faster, more accurate, and easy to maintain.

The application is developed using JSP, HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for the frontend, while Java Servlets are used for backend processing. MySQL Workbench is used for database management, and Apache Tomcat server is used to run the application in the Eclipse development environment. The system follows a structured client-server architecture to ensure proper communication between user interface, server, and database.

The result of the developed Hospital Management System shows that the digital approach reduces manual work, improves data accuracy, and provides better management of hospital records. The system is suitable for small and medium healthcare organizations and can be extended in the future with additional features such as online appointment booking, report generation, and cloud database support.

Index Terms—Hospital Management System, JSP, Java Servlets, MySQL, Tomcat Server, Web Application, Healthcare Management, Database System, Automation.

I. INTRODUCTION

A Hospital Management System is a software application designed to manage the daily operations of a hospital in a systematic and efficient way. Hospitals handle a large amount of information such as patient records, doctor details, prescriptions, medicine stock, and administrative data. Managing all these details manually is difficult, time-consuming, and error-prone. Therefore, a computerized system is required to store, process, and manage hospital information in a secure and organized manner.

In traditional hospital management, most of the work is done using paper files and registers. Patient details are written manually, prescriptions are stored in files, and medicine records are maintained in notebooks. This manual method creates many problems such as data loss, duplication of records, difficulty in searching information, and lack of proper security. In emergency situations, finding patient

history quickly becomes very difficult, which can affect the quality of treatment.

With the growth of information technology, hospitals are moving towards digital systems to improve efficiency and accuracy. A web-based Hospital Management System helps in maintaining records in a centralized database, which can be accessed easily by authorized users. It reduces paperwork, saves time, and improves communication between different departments such as administration, doctors, patients, and pharmacy.

The main objective of this project is to develop a Hospital Management System using JSP, Java Servlets, and MySQL that can manage hospital activities through different modules such as Admin, Patient, Doctor, and Pharmacist. The system is designed to provide secure login, proper data storage, and easy access to information. The Admin module controls the overall system, the Doctor module manages patient details, the Patient module allows viewing of information, and the Pharmacist module handles medicine records.

The proposed system aims to provide a simple, user-friendly, and efficient solution for small and medium hospitals. It reduces manual work, increases accuracy, and ensures better management of hospital data. This project also demonstrates the use of web technologies and database systems in developing real-time applications for healthcare management.

Hospital management is one of the most important aspects of the healthcare industry, as hospitals need to maintain accurate records of patients, doctors, medicines, and administrative activities. In modern healthcare environments, the amount of data generated every day is very large, and handling this data manually becomes difficult. A computerized Hospital Management System helps in organizing information in a structured way so that it can be accessed quickly whenever required.

In many healthcare centers, traditional record-keeping methods are still used, where patient details and treatment history are written on paper. This approach not only consumes more time but also increases the chances of human error. Searching for old records becomes difficult, and maintaining large files requires more physical storage space. Because of these limitations, hospitals require a digital system that can store and manage information efficiently.

A web-based management system provides better flexibility compared to standalone applications because it allows multiple users to access the system at the same time.

Doctors, administrators, and pharmacists can log in to the system using their credentials and perform their respective tasks without interfering with other modules. This improves coordination between different departments and helps in providing better service to patients.

Database management plays a key role in developing a reliable hospital system. By using MySQL as the backend database, all records are stored in tables, which makes data retrieval faster and more accurate. The use of Java Servlets for server-side processing ensures proper communication between the user interface and the database. This architecture provides better performance and makes the system suitable for real-time applications.

Another important advantage of the Hospital Management System is the automation of routine tasks. Activities such as adding patient details, updating doctor information, managing medicine stock, and viewing reports can be done automatically through the system. Automation reduces the workload of hospital staff and minimizes the possibility of mistakes that usually occur in manual calculations and record writing.

The development of this project also focuses on creating a user-friendly interface so that users with basic computer knowledge can easily operate the system. Technologies such as JSP, HTML, CSS, and JavaScript are used to design simple and interactive web pages, while Apache Tomcat server is used to run the application. The system is designed in such a way that it can be extended in the future by adding new modules such as online appointment booking, billing system, and report generation.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In recent years, the use of software applications in the healthcare sector has increased significantly. Hospitals generate a large amount of data related to patients, doctors, medicines, and administrative activities. Managing this data manually is difficult and inefficient. Many researchers have proposed different types of Hospital Management Systems to improve the efficiency, accuracy, and reliability of hospital operations. This section discusses the existing methods, their limitations, and the need for an improved web-based hospital management system.

A. Traditional Manual Hospital Management

In earlier days, hospitals maintained records using paper files and registers. Patient details, prescriptions, billing information, and medicine stock were written manually and stored in physical files. This method required more storage space and made searching for old records very difficult. Many studies have shown that manual systems increase the chances of data loss, duplication, and human error. In emergency situations, finding patient history quickly becomes a major challenge, which may affect the quality of treatment.

Another problem with manual systems is the lack of proper security. Anyone who has access to the files can read or modify the records. This may lead to incorrect information and misuse of sensitive medical data. Because

of these disadvantages, hospitals started moving towards computerized systems.

B. Early Computerized Hospital Systems

The first computerized hospital systems were desktop-based applications developed to store patient and billing information. These systems reduced paperwork and improved data storage compared to manual methods. However, these applications were limited to a single computer and could not be accessed by multiple users at the same time. Doctors, administrators, and pharmacists had to depend on one system, which reduced efficiency.

Research studies show that standalone systems are difficult to maintain because data must be updated separately on each computer. They also lack flexibility and cannot support real-time data sharing between different departments. Due to these limitations, the need for network-based systems increased.

C. Web-Based Hospital Management Systems

With the development of web technologies, modern hospital systems are designed as web-based applications. These systems allow multiple users to access the application through a server using login credentials. Web-based systems provide centralized data storage, which makes management easier and more secure. Researchers have found that web applications are more reliable because they allow real-time updates and reduce the chances of data inconsistency.

Web-based hospital systems also improve communication between different departments. Doctors can view patient details, pharmacists can manage medicine records, and administrators can control the entire system from one platform. This type of system saves time and increases the overall efficiency of hospital operations.

D. Multi-Module Hospital Management Approach

Many existing research works suggest that an effective hospital management system should contain multiple modules to handle different activities. A single module system cannot manage all hospital operations efficiently. Therefore, modern systems include separate modules for administration, patient management, doctor management, and pharmacy management.

The Admin module controls user accounts and system settings, the Doctor module handles patient diagnosis and treatment details, the Patient module stores personal and medical information, and the Pharmacist module manages medicine stock and prescriptions. Integrating all these modules into one system provides better coordination and reduces workload.

E. Need for Proposed System

From the study of existing systems, it is clear that a secure, web-based, multi-module hospital management system is required to overcome the limitations of manual and old computerized methods. The proposed system in this project is developed using JSP, Java Servlets, MySQL, and Apache

Tomcat server. The system provides separate modules for Admin, Patient, Doctor, and Pharmacist, which makes the application easy to use and efficient.

The proposed system reduces manual work, improves accuracy, and provides centralized control over hospital records. It is designed especially for small and medium hospitals where a simple, reliable, and low-cost management solution is required. The system can also be extended in future by adding new features such as online appointment booking, billing system, and cloud database support.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed Hospital Management System is a web-based application designed to automate and manage the daily activities of a hospital in an efficient and secure manner. The system is developed using JSP, Java Servlets, MySQL database, and Apache Tomcat server. The main objective of the proposed system is to replace manual record keeping with a computerized solution that provides fast data access, better security, and easy management of hospital information.

The system follows a client-server architecture in which the user interacts with the web interface, the request is processed by the server, and the data is stored in the database. Different users such as Admin, Doctor, Patient, and Pharmacist can log in to the system using their credentials and perform their respective tasks. Each module is designed separately to maintain proper control and security.

System Architecture: The proposed system follows a three-layer architecture consisting of presentation layer, application layer, and database layer developed using JSP, Java Servlets, and MySQL. The client sends requests through the web browser, which are processed by the Tomcat server using servlets to handle system logic. The server communicates with the database to store and retrieve records, and the processed result is returned to the user interface.

Flow of the System: The system starts with user login where credentials are verified using the database. After successful login, the user is redirected to the respective module such as Admin, Doctor, Patient, or Pharmacist. All operations like add, update, delete, and view are stored in the database to maintain accurate records.

Admin Module: The Admin module controls the entire system and manages doctors, patients, and pharmacists. Admin can add, update, delete, and monitor all records. This module ensures secure access and proper management of system data.

Doctor Module: The Doctor module allows doctors to view patient details, check medical history, and update treatment information. Doctors can also provide prescriptions, which are stored in the database for future reference.

Patient Module: The Patient module stores personal and medical information securely. Patients can login to view their details, prescriptions, and doctor information. This module helps in maintaining organized and accurate patient records.

Pharmacist Module: The Pharmacist module is used to manage medicine records and prescriptions. Pharmacists can add medicines, update stock, and view prescription details.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of Hospital Management System

This module helps in reducing errors in medicine management.

Advantages of Proposed System: The system reduces manual work and improves accuracy by storing data in a centralized database. It provides secure login, fast data access, and easy management of hospital records. The system is user-friendly and can be extended with additional features in the future.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODOLOGY

The implementation of the Hospital Management System is carried out using web-based technologies to provide an efficient and user-friendly environment for managing hospital activities. The system is developed using JSP, HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for the frontend interface, while Java Servlets are used for backend processing. Apache Tomcat server is used to deploy and run the application, and MySQL database is used to store all the records related to patients, doctors, pharmacists, and administrators. The system follows a client-server architecture in which the user interacts with the web browser, and the request is processed by the server before accessing the database.

The methodology of the system is based on role-based access and secure data management. Each user must login with a valid username and password, which are verified using the database. After successful authentication, the user

is redirected to the respective module such as Admin, Doctor, Patient, or Pharmacist. All operations like adding records, updating details, viewing information, and deleting data are processed using Java Servlets and stored in the MySQL database. The Tomcat server handles the communication between the frontend and backend, ensuring smooth data flow and reliable performance of the system.

Fig. 2. Hospital Management System architecture diagram

ER Diagram

Fig. 3. ER diagram of Hospital Management System

Working of the System: The system works based on user login and role-based access. When the user enters the username and password, the system verifies the details using the database. After successful login, the user is redirected to the respective module such as Admin, Doctor, Patient, or Pharmacist. Each module provides different functions like adding records, viewing details, updating data, and deleting information.

Database Management: MySQL database is used to store all hospital records such as patient details, doctor informa-

tion, medicine stock, and login credentials. The database is designed using tables with proper relationships to maintain data accuracy. All data entered by users is stored in the database and can be retrieved whenever required. Using MySQL improves speed, reliability, and security of the system.

Login and Authentication System: The system provides a secure login mechanism for all users. Each user must enter a valid username and password to access the system. The login details are checked with the database using Java Servlets. If the entered information is correct, access is granted; otherwise, an error message is displayed. This authentication process ensures that only authorized users can access the system.

Flow of Data: The flow of data starts from the user interface where the user sends a request through the web browser. The request is received by the Tomcat server and processed using Java Servlets. The servlets communicate with the MySQL database to store or retrieve information. After processing, the result is sent back to the user interface. This flow ensures proper communication between frontend, server, and database.

Server Configuration (Apache Tomcat): Apache Tomcat server is used to run the web application. Tomcat handles all client requests and executes the Java Servlets. The server connects the frontend JSP pages with the backend database. Using Tomcat makes the system reliable and suitable for real-time web applications. The server also helps in managing multiple users at the same time without affecting performance.

Use Case Diagram

Fig. 4. Use Case diagram of Hospital Management System

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Hospital Management System was successfully implemented using JSP, Java Servlets, MySQL, and Apache Tomcat server. The system was tested with different user roles such as Admin, Doctor, Patient, and Pharmacist to verify the functionality of each module. The results show that the system works correctly and allows users to perform operations such as adding records, viewing details, updating information, and managing medicine data without errors.

The login and authentication process was tested to ensure secure access to the system. Only authorized users were

able to login and access their respective modules. The Admin module was able to manage user data, the Doctor module handled patient records, the Patient module displayed personal information, and the Pharmacist module managed medicine details. The database stored all records correctly and retrieved data without delay, which shows that the system performance is reliable.

The system was also tested for multiple operations to check performance and response time. The Apache Tomcat server handled user requests efficiently, and the MySQL database provided fast data storage and retrieval. The results indicate that the proposed system reduces manual work, improves accuracy, and provides better management of hospital data compared to traditional methods. The developed system is suitable for small and medium hospitals and can be extended in the future with additional features.

Fig. 5. User Interface With Different Modules

VI. CONCLUSION

The Hospital Management System was successfully designed and implemented using JSP, Java Servlets, MySQL, and Apache Tomcat server. The developed system provides an efficient way to manage hospital activities such as patient records, doctor details, medicine information, and user authentication. The system replaces the traditional manual method of maintaining records and provides a secure and reliable digital solution. All modules including Admin, Doctor, Patient, and Pharmacist were tested and found to be working correctly without errors. The use of database management ensures accurate storage and fast retrieval of data, which improves the overall performance of hospital operations.

The proposed system helps hospitals reduce paperwork, minimize human errors, and save time in managing daily activities. The centralized database allows authorized users to access information easily, which improves communication between different departments. The login and authentication mechanism provides security for sensitive medical data. The system is user-friendly and can be operated with basic computer knowledge, making it suitable for small and medium hospitals. The results show that the developed application provides better efficiency, reliability, and accuracy compared to manual record management.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

Although the developed Hospital Management System provides all basic functionalities, it can be further improved by adding more advanced features. In future, the system can include online appointment booking, billing management, and report generation to make the application more useful. Cloud database support can also be added to store data securely and allow access from different locations. The system can be extended with mobile application support so that users can access hospital data using smartphones.

Further improvements can include advanced security features such as encryption and OTP-based login to protect sensitive information. Integration with modern technologies like Artificial Intelligence and data analytics can help in better decision making and patient monitoring. The system can also be upgraded to support large hospitals with more users and more data. These enhancements will make the Hospital Management System more powerful, flexible, and suitable for real-time healthcare environments.

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VIII. DISCUSSION:

The developed Hospital Management System was tested with different user roles to evaluate its functionality and performance. The system was able to handle operations such as login authentication, data storage, record updating, and information retrieval without errors. The use of JSP, Java Servlets, MySQL, and Tomcat server provided a stable and reliable environment for the application. The results show that the system reduces manual work, improves accuracy, and allows easy management of hospital data. The performance of the system was satisfactory during testing, and it can be further improved by adding more advanced features in future versions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Workneh, A. Adem, and R. Pradhan, "Understanding Cloud Based Health Care Service with Its Benefits," International Conference on Inventive Communication Computational Technologies (ICICCT), Coimbatore, India, 2018.
- [2] N. Jia and C. Zheng, "Design of Intelligent Medical Interactive System Based on Internet of Things and Cloud Platform," 10th International Conference on Intelligent Human Machine Systems and Cybernetics (IHMSC), Hangzhou, China, 2018.
- [3] K. S. Guruprakash, M. Jaiganesh, V. Vijey Nathan, and R. Sathya, "Location and Temporal based Multi-Cloud Package Selection for Enterprise," Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1066-1075, 2021.
- [4] T. Vigneshwaran, K. S. Guruprakash, K. Thaslima Nasreen, and M. Supraja, "Effective Framework for Real Time Video Face Recognition System," Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 680-684, 2020.
- [5] K. Sudharson, A. Mudassar Ali, and N. Partheeban, "NUI TECH Natural User Interface Technique for Emulating Computer Hardware," International Journal of Pharmacy and Technology, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 23598-23606, 2016.
- [6] J. A. Jasmine, V. N. Jenipher, J. S. R. Jimreeves, K. Ravindran, and D. Dhinakaran, "A Traceability Set up Using Digitalization of Data and Accessibility," 2020 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Sustainable Systems (ICISS), pp. 907-910, 2020.
- [7] R. Sivan and Z. A. Zukarnain, "Security and Privacy in Cloud-Based E-Health System," Symmetry, vol. 13, no. 5, 2021.
- [8] R. Jeena, G. Dhanalakshmi, S. I. Sherly, S. Ashwini, and R. Vidhya, "A Novel Approach for Healthcare Information System using Cloud," International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering, vol. 9, no. 6, 2021.
- [9] M. Sha and M. P. Rahamathulla, "Cloud-based Healthcare Data Management Framework," KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems, vol. 14, no. 3, 2020.
- [10] K. Dhinakaran, M. Nivetha, N. Duraimurugan, and D. C. J. W. Wise, "Cloud Based Smart Healthcare Management System Using Blue Eyes Technology," 2020 International Conference on Electronics and Sustainable Communication Systems (ICESC), pp. 409-414, 2020.
- [11] K. S. Shalini, R. Shobana, S. Leelavathy, and V. Sridevi, "A Cloud Based Approach for Health Care Management," International Journal of Chemical Sciences, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 2927-2932, 2016.
- [12] K. Makanyadevi, S. Kandasamy, S. V. E., R. Sasikumar, and A. Firos, "Efficient Healthcare Assisting Cloud Storage Strategy using Fog Prioritization Logic," Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1059-1066, 2021.
- [13] O. Warghade et al., "Cloud Based Secure Multi Owner Hospital Management System," International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, vol. 9, no. 1, 2020.
- [14] R. Sachdeva and C. Monga, "Cloud Based ICT in Healthcare Management," IJCSC, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1-6, 2018.
- [15] B. Wukkadada and V. P. Saiswani, "Online Healthcare System Using Cloud Computing and Artificial Intelligence," IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering, pp. 40-43, 2018.
- [16] K. S. Guruprakash et al., "Optimized Workload Assigning System Using Particle Swarm Optimization," International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, vol. 29, no. 7, 2020.
- [17] M. De Donno, K. Tange, and N. Dragoni, "Foundations and Evolution of Modern Computing Paradigms: Cloud, IoT, Edge, and Fog," IEEE Access, 2020.
- [18] J. Liang, M. Zhang, and V. C. M. Leung, "Reliable Trust Computing Mechanism Based on Multisource Feedback and Fog Computing," IEEE Internet of Things Journal, 2020.
- [19] D. Dhinakaran and P. M. Joe Prathap, "Ensuring Privacy of Data in Collaborative ARM," Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, Springer, 2022.
- [20] S. Arun and K. Sudharson, "DEFECT: Discover and Eradicate Fool Around Node in Emergency Network," Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing, 2020.
- [21] J. Liu et al., "Max-Min Energy Balance in Wireless-Powered Fog-Cloud Computing Networks," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, 2020.
- [22] J. Li, W. Yao, Y. Zhang, H. Qian, and J. Han, "Flexible and Fine-Grained Attribute Based Data Storage in Cloud Computing," IEEE Transactions on Services Computing, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 785-796, 2017.